

A Closed-Loop Neuromodulation Chipset with 0.0009mm²-0.36μW/Ch Recording Frontend and 0.075mm²-6.76μW Seizure Classification Backend

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Abstract

This work presents a closed-loop neuromodulation chipset, integrating 64 analog frontends (AFEs) featuring a novel IDAC-embedded OTA, a lightweight feature extraction unit, a Sparse Projection Oblique Randomer Forest (SPORF) classifier, and 4 high-voltage (HV) compliant current stimulators. Each AFE occupies 0.0009mm² and consumes 0.36μW, the smallest area and lowest power reported to date for ECoG recording (BW≤1kHz). Verified with CHB-MIT [1] and ETHZ [2] databases, the digital backend (DBE) occupies 0.075mm², consumes 6.76μW and achieves event-based sensitivity and specificity of 94.93%/98.58% and 99.55%/99.97%, respectively, in patient-specific scenarios.

Introduction

Closed-loop neuromodulation for epilepsy patients (>50 million worldwide) can monitor brain activity to detect seizure onset and deliver targeted stimulation to suppress clinical symptoms. A compact and energy-efficient implementation is essential to improve therapeutic efficacy and treatment outcomes. Prior work has aimed to develop such systems, but either do not scale well to high channel count [3], lack stimulation [4] [5] or HV compliance [6], or need large on-chip classifier memory [7]. This work introduces a compact and low-power chipset to address these issues and provide digital-intensive always-on brain state monitoring and HV-compliant event-driven neuromodulation.

System Architecture

The proposed closed-loop neuromodulation chipset integrates 64 AFEs for signal conditioning and digitization, a lightweight DBE for feature extraction and classification, and 4 current stimulators for neuromodulation (Fig. 1). Each stimulation channel is implemented with an IDAC and a current driver. The IDAC is integrated with the AFE and DBE in 28-nm CMOS technology (Chip A) for improved area and power efficiency, while the driver is realized in 180-nm BCD technology (Chip B) to achieve HV compliance.

Each recording channel integrates an AC-coupled OTA-C based incremental $\Sigma\Delta$ ADC with IDAC feedback to achieve high area efficiency (0.0009mm²/ch), high input impedance (1.59T Ω at 1Hz), and rail-to-rail electrode DC offset rejection. Input reset switches, normally OFF, are activated to short OTA inputs to the common-mode voltage (V_B) when the ADC approaches saturation [8]. Multi-channel frontends with IDAC-based $\Sigma\Delta$ ADCs present two critical challenges (Fig. 2-top): 1) inter-channel noise coupling due to IDAC switching via shared bias lines, and 2) channel gain (or input range (IR)) non-uniformity across the array. To address these issues, this work embeds the feedback IDAC directly within the OTA's input pair (Fig. 2-bottom). This novel approach splits each input transistor into two smaller devices (a and b), and connects the drains of the smaller pair b to the required branch based on the comparator output ($Q_{n,p}$) for effective feedback. To a first-order approximation, the channel gain is solely set by geometries and remains unaffected by bias conditions (Fig. 2). Also, this design does not require the dummy path commonly employed in traditional IDACs to improve transient response when feedback currents are switched [9]. The folded-cascode OTA uses a 0.7V supply for the input stage and 1/10th input current bias for the output stage to save power (Fig. 3). Load PMOS transistors are cross-coupled and self-biased by the OTA output, eliminating the requirement for an auxiliary CMFB amplifier [10]. Low-V_t devices minimize output common-mode variation across corners.

The feature extraction unit (FEU) selects up to 5 channels and can provide: (1) spectral features, including phase locking value (PLV) and phase-amplitude coupling (PAC), and (2) temporal features, including line length, maximum, minimum, average, and approximated interquartile range (Fig. 4). Spectral features are extracted using a low-power multiplier-less Hoda wavelet [11]. The neural signals are pre-decimated through a multi-rate LPF, minimizing the number of wavelet taps and allowing for flexible feature band selectivity. A dedicated computation unit calculates PLV and PAC from the filtered signals, employing light sine/cosine extraction (LSCE) to avoid the need for phase extraction and α Max- β Min approximation for efficient magnitude calculation [12].

This work uses a SPORF classifier [13] to obtain similar accuracy to deep learning (DL) models [14], [15] while maintaining the power efficiency of tree-based models [7], [16]. Model coefficients are constrained to ternary values [-1,0,1] during training to avoid energy-intensive multiplications during inference and significantly reduce memory (-47%) when compared to 10-bit models with similar performance (Fig. 5). A multi-path hardware implementation of the tree removes the need to store node addresses, leaf and class information, which reduces the memory by another 10%. The model requires only 570 bits to store all parameters. A reduced set of features is used by performing model-specific feature selection during training, resulting in a lightweight FEU.

Each neurostimulator consists of a segmented 8b IDAC (4+4), a push-pull stage, and an HV driver (Fig. 1). Arbitrary waveforms can be programmed to reduce the residual artifact duration [17]. To improve power efficiency by 44%, a gain of 8 is implemented for the HV current driver (Fig. 6, anodic part not shown). A regulated cascode topology boosts the output impedance, with bulk modulation employed in the impedance-boosting loop, improving output swing and loop stability compared to conventional gate feedback. A series resistor limits potential large current flow through the bulk terminal during start-up. The input branch employs a similarly regulated cascode with replica bias, ensuring high mirror accuracy through matched V_{DS} .

Measurements

The chipset prototype was fabricated in TSMC's 28nm HPC+ and 180nm HV-BCD (Fig. 7). Each recording channel occupies 0.0009mm² and consumes 0.36μW. Fig. 8 shows measured recording channel performance, with an input-referred noise of 5.3μV_{rms} (1-500Hz) for a grounded input, and a THD of -47.9dB for a 2mV_{pp} 100Hz sine input. The classification performance was verified on seizure detection (CHB-MIT and ETHZ datasets), achieving 94.93%/98.58% sensitivity and 99.55%/99.97% specificity (Fig. 9). The input sampling frequency is 1kHz (derived from 1024kHz master clock) and the feature window is 2s. Measured stimulator output, shown in Fig. 6-bottom, demonstrates rapid artifact recovery and HV compliance (9V_{pp}). Performance summary and comparison to other works are presented in Table I. Fig. 10 highlights that our recording channel achieves the smallest area and lowest power among neural readouts with ECoG bandwidth (≤1kHz), while the DBE consumes the least power and achieves DL-like sensitivity in seizure detection.

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Fig. 1. System diagram of proposed neuromodulation chipset.

Fig. 2. Conventional (top) and proposed (bottom) multi-channel acquisition systems, and IDAC-embedded input pair.

Fig. 3. Circuit schematic of OTA with embedded IDAC.

Fig. 4. Feature extraction unit.

Fig. 5. Sparse projection oblique randomer forest classifier.

Fig. 6. Circuit schematic of HV driver (anodic part not shown for simplicity), and measured output waveforms with $6k\Omega + 470nF$ load.

Fig. 7. Chip micrographs, layout of single-channel AFE, and measurement setup.

Fig. 8. Measured channel performance (input-referred noise (IRN) and linearity) of recording frontend.

Fig. 9. DBE measurement results.

TABLE I. Performance Summary and Comparison

AFE	This work	Wu TBCAS'24	Carlino TBCAS'24	Huang JSSC'22	Paz. TBCAS'22	Shin JSSC'22
Technology [nm]	28	65	180	22	130	65
Power supply [V]	0.7/0.9	1	1/1.8	0.6/0.8	1.2/3.3	1.2
Channel count	64	16	32:1	256:16	64	256:4
Area [mm ²]	0.0009	0.017	0.0018	0.001	0.018	0.004
Power [μW]	0.35	5.56	4.51	1.61	1.1	1.51
Bandwidth [Hz]	1-500	1-1k	1-500	1-500	1-500	1-500
Input chopping	NO	YES	YES	YES	YES	YES
Noise [μV _{rms}]	5.3	1	1.71	1.55	2.1	3.2
EDO Range	Rail-to-rail	--	--	156mV _{pp}	±1.5V	100mV _{pp}
Z _{in} @1Hz	1.59TΩ	20MΩ	108MΩ	43MΩ	250MΩ	24.5MΩ
DBE	This work	Zhang JSSC'22	Liu JSSC'22	Shin JSSC'22		
Technology [nm]	28	40	55	65		
Power supply [V]	0.75	0.7	0.68	1.2		
Ch./classification	5	16	16	64		
Area [mm ²]/Memory [kB]	0.075/0.091	1.43/134	0.98/8	1.58/2.93		
Power [μW]	6.76	n/a	25.8	271.35		
Energy/class. [nJ]	84.57	970	72	227		
Classifier	SPORF	SVM	HF-CNN	NeuralTree		
Features	Max,Min,Mean, LL,IQR,PAC,PLV	SE	LL,SE,NN	PLV,PAC,SE,HFO, LL,LMP,Hjorth		
Sen./Spec. [%]	94.93/99.55	100/99.5	100/99.3	95.6/96.8		

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Fig. 10. Scatter plots of state-of-the-art ECoG recording channel's power and area (top), and DBE's power and sensitivity (bottom).